

COMPOSITION, STRUCTURE OF THE PROPERTY OF THE ENTERPRISE AND SOURCES OF ITS ORIGIN. INCOME ACCOUNTING ON THE EXAMPLE OF "PRIORA" LLP

Nurmagambetova L.,

*Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
KEEU named after. M. Dulatova*

Yarochkina Ye.

*Candidate of Historical Sciences, Associate Professor
KRU named after A. Baitursynov*

Abstract

The article discusses the activities of an enterprise that carries out entrepreneurial activities, regardless of the form of ownership, exist in order to receive income. The income of any enterprise is formed as a result of the implementation of the main and secondary activities. The process of income management largely affects the financial condition of the enterprise, as well as the list of regulatory documents governing the procedure for their accounting.

Keywords: income accounting, property, balance sheet, "Priora" LLP.

Introduction. It is customary to call the property of an enterprise buildings, structures, vehicles, machinery and equipment and other material assets used by the enterprise to carry out its financial and economic activities. The value of property in practice during the reporting period can both increase and decrease. The cost increases upon receipt of the property, or its modernization, decreases upon disposal. The value of the property is to be assessed by examining its composition as well as its structure. Changing the structure of property can reveal the sources of its occurrence. To analyze the composition and structure of the property of the enterprise, the information contained in the report on the financial position of the organization (balance sheet) is subject to disclosure.

An analysis of the property structure makes it clear to what extent the enterprise has certain funds and requirements to cover obligations, and what proportion of the enterprise's current assets occupy the balance sheet in the overall structure of the asset [1].

Material and methods. To reveal the indicated problem of the study, the author used various sources. The main material for the study was various data on the financial condition of the enterprise, on the example of Priora LLP, its revenue. The entity provided information on its balance sheet. The data provided by the enterprise helped to consider the share of working capital, asset, balance sheet and other state of the organization. To reveal the indicated problem of the study, the author used various sources. The main material for the study was various data on the financial condition of the enterprise, on the example of Priora LLP, its revenue. The entity provided information on its balance sheet. The data provided by the enterprise helped to consider the share of working capital, asset, balance sheet and other state of the organization. Exploring the economic processes of general scientific methods of cognition,

structural-functional and comparative approaches, collection of facts and observation, analysis and synthesis, a systematic approach, when studying the state of the financial well-being of an organization or, on the contrary, its failure. They also tried to predict the possible risks of the enterprise using the logical method, the historical method showed the place of the enterprise that it occupies in the modern structure of the region's economy.

Results. Having considered the composition and structure of the property of Priora LLP, we can conclude that the main share of the company's assets for the period 2020-2022 is occupied by short-term receivables. There is an increase in receivables in 2021 compared to 2020, however, in 2022, short-term receivables are reduced by 34,654.50 thousand tenge, and amount to 393,975.70 thousand tenge, but remain higher than this indicator in 2020 by 112,031.49 thousand tenge. The share of receivables in the structure of the company's assets is kept at the same level, within 85% -90%. So the share of receivables in 2020 amounted to 87.52%, and in 2022 - 85.35%, in 2021 this indicator was higher than in 2022 by 5.10%, and amounted to 90.46% (this information presented in the table of the composition and structure of the property of Priora LLP).

Cash in Priora LLP at the end of the reporting period ranged from 0.02 to 0.98% of the total asset structure of Priora LLP. So, the amount of cash as of December 31, 2022 amounted to 108.87 thousand tenge or 0.02% of the total value of the company's assets, for example, this indicator in 2020 amounted to 3 152.19 thousand tenge or 0.98% from the value of the property of the organization. But, not always, a decrease in the amount of cash in the accounts and cash of the enterprise at the end of the reporting period indicates that the enterprise is in need of working capital. Often, this indicator must be compared with the amount of liabilities, since with a rational distribution of funds, there should not be a large balance in their accounts.

Table 1
Composition and structure of the assets of the balance sheet of Priora LLP, thousand tenge

Name	As of the end					Changes from				
	2020 year	%	2021 year	%	2022 year	%	2020 year	%	2021 year	%
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Cash	3 152,19	0,98	202,28	0,04	108,87	0,02	-3 043,33	-0,95	-93,41	-0,02
Short-term accounts receivable	281 944,20	87,52	428 630,20	90,46	393 975,70	85,35	112 031,49	-2,17	-34 654,50	-5,10
Stocks	27 192,56	8,44	20 538,35	4,33	48 471,53	10,50	21 278,97	2,06	27 933,18	6,17
Current tax assets	79,28	0,02	78,74	0,02	536,07	0,12	456,80	0,09	457,33	0,10
Other current assets	4 326,09	1,34	21 202,55	4,47	17 348,62	3,76	13 022,52	2,42	-3 853,94	-0,72
Total current assets	316 694,33	98,31	470 652,13	99,33	460 440,78	99,75	143 746,45	1,44	-10 211,35	0,43
fixed assets	5 445,45	1,69	3 083,46	0,65	1 133,96	0,25	-4 311,49	-1,44	-1 949,50	-0,41
Intangible assets			113,75		8,75		8,75	0,00	-105,00	0,00
Total non-current assets	5 445,45	1,69	3 197,21	0,65	1 142,71	0,25	-4 302,74	-1,44	-2 054,50	-0,41
Total property	322 139,78	100,00	473 849,34	99,98	461 583,49	100,00	139 443,71	0,00	-12 265,85	0,02

From the data in the table it can be seen that in the structure of the assets of the enterprise, current assets occupy a large part, this indicates the mobility of assets, which accelerates their turnover and strengthens the solvency of the enterprise [2]. The stocks of the enterprise, along with cash, are the working capital of the enterprise, and an analysis of their composition and structure can show how quickly their value can be turned into cash, or it will be attributed to the cost of production, in which case the cost will turn into cash only after payment for the goods sold. From the data in the table it can be seen that in the structure of the assets

of the enterprise, current assets occupy a large part, this indicates the mobility of assets, which accelerates their turnover and strengthens the solvency of the enterprise [3].

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Table 2

Composition and structure of inventories of Priora LLP, thousand tenge

Name	As of the end						Changes from	
	2020 year	%	2021 year	%	2022 year	%	2020 year	2021 year
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Raw materials	23 328	86	15 311	75	14 323	30	-9 005	-988
Finished products	1 826	7	1 903	9	1 694	3	-131	-209
Goods	2 031	7	3 324	16	31 959	66	29 927	28 635
Other materials	7	0	0	0	531	1	524	531
TOTAL	27 193	100	20 538	100	48 507	100	21 315	27 969

Based on Table 2, we can conclude that in the cost of inventory of the enterprise, most of the raw materials and materials for the production of products, as well as goods for sale. If in 2020 the share of goods in the cost of all inventory was 7%, then this figure in 2022 was 66%. Such a large balance of goods for sale indicates that either the sale of the goods was not reflected in the accounting accounts on time, or the enterprise concluded an agreement for the supply of goods in January 2022 at the end of the year. In any case, the balance of inventories at the end of the period indicates the irrational use of funds and fuzzy income planning, and as a result leads to an increase in the amount of CIT, in view of the fact that corporate income tax is accrued on the amount of inventories remaining at the end of the period. tax.

The share of raw materials and materials for the period 2020-2022, on the contrary, is decreasing and in 2022 it is 30%, which is 56% less than in 2020 and 45% less than in 2021. As of December 31, 2022, the amount of raw materials and supplies is 14,323.00 thousand tenge, which is 9,005.00 thousand tenge less than in 2020 and 988 thousand tenge less than in 2021. The information that is given in the liabilities side of the balance sheet allows you to determine what changes have occurred in the structure of equity and borrowed capital, how much long-term and short-term borrowed funds are involved in the turnover of the enterprise, that is, the liability shows where the funds came from, to whom the company owes them. The financial condition of the enterprise largely depends on what funds it has at its disposal and where they are invested. Analyzing the table of the composition and structure of the liabilities of the balance sheet, it can be seen that the main

part of the sources of the property of Priora LLP are other short-term liabilities. In the total share of all property in 2022, other short-term liabilities account for 50.51% and amount to 283,843.00 thousand tenge, which is 22.43% less than in 2020 and 11.58% less than in 2021.

The decrease in the share of short-term liabilities has a positive effect on the financial condition of the enterprise as a whole.

It is possible to assume that this amount consists of other accounts payable to legal entities, and from the dynamics tending to reduce this amount, we can say that the company covers its obligations to a certain extent. The retained earnings of Priora LLP in 2022 is 177,643.09 thousand tenge, which is more than the indicator of retained earnings in 2020 by 110,108.19 thousand tenge, and by 59,196.48 thousand tenge more than retained earnings in 2021 year. Increasing the company's profit also indicates the stabilization of the financial situation. The share of retained earnings of the enterprise in 2020 was 20.96% in the total share of all sources of the enterprise's property. During the period under review, there is an increase in the share of retained earnings.

So in 2022, the share is 38.49%, which is 17.52% more than in 2020 and 13.49% more than in 2021. Unlike retained earnings and other short-term liabilities, short-term accounts payable are increasing, both in value terms and in specific weights. In 2021, this indicator increased and amounted to 31,978.92 or 6.75% of the total balance sheet liability. In 2022, short-term accounts payable amounted to 41,589.79 thousand tenge or 9.01%, which is more than this indicator in 2020 by 33,573.44 thousand tenge or 6.52%.

Table 3
Composition and structure of liabilities in the balance sheet of Priora LLP, thousand tenge

Наименование	As of the end							Changes from			
	2020 year	%	2021 year	%	2022 year	%	2020 year	%	2021 year	%	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
Tax liabilities	11 208,74	3,48	28 818,77	6,08	8 824,50	1,91	-2 384,24	-1,57	-19 994,27	-4,17	
Liabilities for other mandatory and voluntary payments	328,04	0,10	304,46	0,06	294,35	0,06	-33,69	-0,04	-10,10	0,00	
Short-term accounts payable	8 016,35	2,49	31 978,92	6,75	41 589,79	9,01	33 573,44	6,52	9 610,87	2,26	
Other current liabilities	234 954,64	72,94	294 203,48	62,09	233 134,66	50,51	-1 819,98	-22,43	-61 068,83	-11,58	
Total current liabilities	254 507,78	79,01	355 305,63	74,98	283 843,30	61,49	29 335,52	-17,51	-71 462,33	-13,49	
Authorized capital	97,10	0,03	97,10	0,02	97,10	0,02	0,00	-0,01	0,00	0,00	
Retained earnings, uncovered loss	67 534,90	20,96	118 446,61	25,00	177 643,09	38,49	110 108,19	17,52	59 196,48	13,49	
Total sources of property	322 139,78	100,00	473 849,34	100,00	461 583,49	100,00	139 443,71	0,00	-12 265,85	0,00	

Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that the property of the enterprise consists mainly of retained earnings of the enterprise, as well as other short-term liabilities, the authorized capital of Priora LLP is 97.1 thousand tenge, and did not increase in the period from 2020 to 2022. There are no borrowed funds from financial organizations in Priora LLP, which is also one of the positive factors in the company's activities. An indicator characterizing the ability of enterprises to pay for their obligations is the amount of own working capital. This value is calculated by formula (3).

$$\text{COK} = \text{TA} - \text{TO}, \quad (3)$$

Where TA - current assets of the enterprise, tenge;

TO - short-term liabilities of the enterprise (current liabilities), tenge.

As of 01.01.2022, the amount of own working capital amounted to 176,597.48 thousand tenge, this value in 2021 is 115,346.50 thousand tenge, an increase in the amount of own working capital indicates that the company strengthens the position of assets and increases the ability to assets to cover their liabilities. From the table of the composition and structure of the sources of formation of the enterprise's property, you can see the amount of retained earnings, but this amount falls into the statement of financial position, based on another report that makes up the financial statements of the enterprise. The profit and loss statement of the enterprise shows what income the organization received during the reporting period, and what items of expenditure occurred.

Table – 4

Profit and loss statement of Priora LLP for 2020-2022, thousand tenge

Indicators		2020 year	2021 year	2022 year
Income from sales of products and services	010	891 059	969 306	708 217
Cost of goods sold and services rendered	020	796 451	843 292	573 750
Gross profit (line 010 - line 020)	030	94 608	126 014	134 467
Financing income	040	-	-	-
Other income	050	1 970	1 130	981
Expenses for the sale of products and the provision of services	060	-	-	105
Administrative expenses	070	43 491	31 056	39 511
Financing costs	080	-	-	-
other expenses	090	4 725	32 016	21 282
1	2	3	4	5
Share of profit/loss of organizations accounted for using the equity method	100	-	-	-
Profit (loss) for the period from continuing operations (line 030+line 040+line 050-line 060 – line 070 - line 080 - line 090+/- line 100)	110	48 362	64 072	74 549
Profit (loss) from discontinued operations	120	-	-	-
Profit (loss) before tax (line 110+/-line 120)	130	48 362	64 072	74 549
Corporate income tax expense	140	6 336	13 161	15 353
Net profit (loss) for the period (line 130 - line 140) before minority interest	150	42 027	50 912	59 196
Minority share	160	-	-	-
Total profit (total loss) for the period (line 150-line 160)	200	42 027	50 912	59 196
Earnings per share	210	-	-	-
Other comprehensive income	220	-	-	-
Share of enterprises using the equity method	230	-	-	-
Total Comprehensive Income	240	42 027	50 912	59 196

The profit and loss statement of the Partnership shows that during the analyzed period there is a decrease in income from the sale of products and the provision of services. So, gross income in 2022 amounted to 708,217.00 thousand tenge, which is 182,842.00 thousand tenge less than in 2020, such a decrease is due to the coronavirus pandemic announced by the World Health Organization, many deliveries of goods were not made, Accordingly, the Partnership did not receive additional income. However, despite the decrease in income, the cost of goods sold and services rendered also decreased, the cost in 2022 decreased by 222,701.00 thousand tenge compared to 2020, and amounted to 573,750.00 thousand tenge. We also see that the

amount of other income of the organization has decreased. In 2020, the Partnership received income in the amount of 1,970.00 thousand tenge, however, other income by 2022 was reduced to the amount of 981.00 thousand tenge. Along with a decrease in income, cost and other income of the enterprise, there is instability in the increase and decrease in administrative and other expenses. Considering the administrative expenses item, it can be seen that in 2020 the general administrative expenses of the enterprise amounted to 43,491.00 thousand tenge, in 2021 there was a saving on this item in the amount of 12,435.00 thousand tenge compared to 2020, however, in 2022 we see an increase in the amount of administrative expenses in the amount of

8,455.00 thousand tenge compared to 2021. Other expenses of the partnership also tend to unjustifiably decrease and then increase. So in 2020, the item other expenses amounted to 4,725.00 thousand tenge, in 2021 this item increased almost 7 times and amounted to 32,016.00 thousand tenge, in 2022, other expenses decreased by 10,734.00 thousand tenge, and amounted to 21,282.00 thousand tenge, however, this amount is almost 5 times more than in 2020.

This raises the question, when receiving a high amount of profit, other expenses of the enterprise are low, when receiving low gross income, other expenses increase. This indicates incorrect cost planning, and a lack of control over the expenditure of the enterprise's funds [4].

One of the main tasks of the activities of the organization is the receipt of profit. However, not always the financial result of the work of an enterprise is positive. Accounting for financial results and the use of profits allows the organization of control over current activities and plan further work. Each organization for internal control sums up the results of its activities. Such results are called financial results. It can turn out to be positive or negative. A positive result is also called the profit of an enterprise. It arises in a situation when income exceeds expenses. In other words, organization works "in plus". Profit as a whole signals the effectiveness of activities, however, if the analysis to analyze its dynamics (statistics for several years), then it is possible to reveal the growth or fall of its size, which speaks of results of work [5]. Loss appears in a situation when incomes do not cover expenses and enterprises functions "in the minus". The emergence of this phenomenon is an alarming signal for management, saying about inefficiency and the need to take measures to improve work. The implementation of accounting for financial results and the use of income is necessary for control activities of the company, tactical and strategic planning, as well as for external use so that those who can use it to make a decision on investing the money of the investor or about the issuance of a credit to a banking organization. Accounting provides data for the analysis of the results of work. To account for the results of activities, there are several accounts, and their application depends on whether what kind of activity will get you income and incur expenses.

Income and expenses are divided into two groups:

- 1) from ordinary activities;
- 2) from other activities.

Activity, written in the constituent documents and characteristic for the organization, is usual. To account for financial results from ordinary activities, account 5710 "Retained earnings (uncovered loss) and subaccount to him. Profit or loss from ordinary activities is reflected in the records:

Wire Content

Dt 6010 Kt 5710 from the profit of the organization

Dt 5710 Kt 7010 organization received a loss

Other types of activities include those that are not characteristic in work those firms. They can be called secondary incomes or races, since the organization

from the beginning does not plan to carry these expenses or receive such income.

Other incomes include:

- benefits from investments in valuable papers;
- positive differences that arise with the growth of the exchange rate;
- surplus, revealed in the course of inventory of property;
- credit debt written off in connection with the expiration of the limitation period for collection, etc.

Under other races they say:

- fines, penalties, forfeits, payments to counterparties or to the state budget;
- negative differences, appearing in connection with the fall of the currency exchange rate;
- Debt for the expiration of the statute of limitations, etc. Для учета прочих доходов и расходов предусмотрены счет 6280 «Прочий доход» и субсчета к нему. Прибыль или убыток от прочей деятельности отражаются записями:

Wire Content

Dt 6280 Kt 5710 from the profit of the organization

Dt 5710 Kt 7010 organization received a loss

Итоговый финансовый результат определяется по окончании года и отражается по счетам 5610 «Нераспределенная прибыль (непокрытый убыток) отчетного года»

Wire Content

Dt 6010 Kt 5610 better net profit

Dt 5610 Kt 7010 for fix siro van loss at the end of the year

Profit is a distinct result of the firm's activities. But its receipt is not enough for further growth. In this regard, it is necessary to take into account the rational use of the profit. Net profit is recorded on account 5610 and arises after the payment of income tax. In the future, pure profit is distributed. Direction of net income defines management, they include:

- 1) repayment of losses that have arisen in past periods;
- 2) formation of a reserve capital;
- 3) payment of dividends to the company's participants.

The results of the company's activities are information that the company's management needs for internal control [6]. The result of the work can be either positive (profit) or negative (loss). Profit is usually perceived as an indicator of the effective operation of the enterprise. But a more accurate estimate can only be obtained by analyzing the dynamics of financial results. The decrease in the level of profit from year to year clearly speaks of the financial problems of the company.

If the profit remains at approximately the same level for several years, this also indicates a lack of efficiency of the enterprise. The work of the company can be recognized as effective only in case of positive dynamics, if the profit increases annually.

The appearance of uncovered losses is a wake-up call for any enterprise. It demonstrates the inefficiency of activities and requires the adoption of a set of

measures aimed at improving performance. An increase in the volume of losses indicates that management is not taking serious action to eliminate the problems that led to this situation. The result is usually the bankruptcy of the company.

If losses cannot be avoided, but their level decreases annually, this may indicate that the measures taken have been effective. But it may be worth considering additional options for getting out of a difficult situation. Accounting for financial results and their analysis is necessary for tactical and strategic planning. Depending on the results obtained, measures are developed that allow increasing the level of profit [7].

The study of indicators allows you to understand: whether the company correctly uses existing financial assets and liabilities; how significant is the impact of net profit on the structure of the organization's own capital; whether the expenses of the enterprise correspond to the level of existing profit; what factors positively influence the financial result, and what hinder its growth. Thus, the indicators of the company's financial results make it possible to evaluate the company's economic activity in all areas separately: production, sales, financial and investment activities. The analysis of these indicators is the basis for the economic development of the company and the stability of relationships with partners and contractors.

Along with the assessment of the profit and loss statement, indicators of financial results are such indicators as profitability and liquidity. The profitability indicator is an integral part of the analysis of financial results and plays an important role for the enterprise, showing its profitability [8].

Conclusion. Having considered the composition and structure of the property of Priora LLP, we can conclude that the main share of the company's assets for the period 2020-2022 is occupied by short-term receivables. There is an increase in receivables in 2021 compared to 2020, however, in 2022, short-term receivables are reduced by 34,654.50 thousand tenge, and amount to 393,975.70 thousand tenge, but remain higher than this indicator in 2020 by 112,031.49 thousand tenge. The share of receivables in the structure of the company's assets is kept at the same level, within 85% -90%.

Thus, the share of receivables in 2020 amounted to 87.52%, and in 2022 - 85.35%, in 2021 this indicator was higher than in 2022 by 5.10%, and amounted to 90.46%. Cash in Priora LLP at the end of the reporting period ranged from 0.02 to 0.98% of the total asset structure of Priora LLP. So, the amount of cash as of December 31, 2022 amounted to 108.87 thousand tenge or 0.02% of the total value of the company's assets, for example, this indicator in 2020 amounted to 3 152.19 thousand tenge or 0.98% from the value of the property of the organization. But, not always, a decrease in the amount of cash in the accounts and cash of the enterprise at the end of the reporting period indicates that the enterprise is in need of working capital. Often, this indicator must be compared with the amount of liabilities, since with a rational distribution of funds, there should not be a large balance in their accounts.

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